

LABOR MARKET ETHICS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF DIGITALIZATION**Sikorskyi Yu.***PhD in Economics**Spetsdetalservis LLC, Institute of International Relations, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Kyiv, Ukraine**<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6049-8887>***ABSTRACT**

Digitization brings numerous changes to sectors of the economy, in particular, to the labor market. Key in this context is the issue of ethics in the labor market, which is affected by the introduction of digital technologies. The purpose of the article is to study the changes in ethical norms and principles arising in the labor market as a result of the introduction of digital technologies. The article examines the impact of digital transformation on business and the importance of digital ethics in today's technological environment. The rapid development of technology, particularly artificial intelligence, opens up new opportunities for innovation and efficiency, but also raises serious ethical challenges. The COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated digitalization, forcing companies to adapt their processes to new conditions. According to PwC, 50% of companies consider themselves prepared for digital ethics, 33% of companies evaluate their digital transformation positively. As part of the effective integration of digital ethics, PwC recommends several steps: development and implementation of a code of digital ethics, integration of ethical standards into management systems, employee training, application of ethics in product design, and value orientation when developing new products. The toolkit for managing the ethics of the labor market is proposed, which includes the analysis of the current situation, the development of ethical principles and norms, the creation of regulatory and political mechanisms, the implementation of educational programs, the use of technological tools for monitoring, auditing and responsibility for violations of ethical standards. It is noted that the proposed toolkit should be flexible and adapted to new conditions, ensuring a fair and ethical environment for all participants of the labor market. It is emphasized that the successful integration of digital ethics will contribute to building trust, enhancing reputation and achieving long-term success in the digital economy. The proposed research can be useful to analysts, international organizations, business associations, state and local authorities.

Keywords: ethics; digitization; Artificial Intelligence; monitoring; stakeholder.

Introduction. The labor market, as an integral part of the economic system, is undergoing significant transformations under the influence of digitalization. Digitalization, which includes the implementation of digital technologies in all areas of life, changes not only the structure of the labor market, but also ethical standards and norms of behavior. In this context, new challenges and opportunities arise that require in-depth analysis and discussion. Modern digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence, significantly change work processes and requirements for employees. This leads to the appearance of new professions and the disappearance of old ones, changes in the forms of employment and working conditions. At the same time, these changes raise ethical questions related to the rights of employees, the level of their security, the preservation of confidentiality and the fair distribution of resources. One of the key aspects of ethics in the labor market in the digital environment is to ensure equal opportunities for all employees. This includes issues of access to training and reskilling, which is particularly relevant in the context of rapid technological change. It is also important to consider the ethical implications of automation, which can lead to mass layoffs and increased social inequality. In addition, digitalization affects the work-life balance of employees. Thanks to remote work technologies, many people get the opportunity to work from anywhere in the world, which contributes to the flexibility of the workplace. However, it can also blur the lines between work and leisure, causing emotional burnout and stress. Accordingly, the question of studying the ethical aspects of the labor

market in conditions of digitalization, analyzing the challenges faced by employees and employers, and forming proposals for possible solutions to ensure fair working conditions becomes urgent. Attention should be focused on studying how technological changes affect ethical norms and what steps can be taken to minimize the negative effects of these changes.

Review of previous studies. Digitalization significantly changes all aspects of the labor market, including personnel policy, professional development, and forms of work. Modern studies focus on various aspects of these changes, in particular on the ethical challenges arising in the process of digitalization. Kryshchal H., Bryukhovetska I. E. Panin [1] emphasize the importance of integrating digital technologies into the personnel policy of organizations. The authors note that digitalization contributes to the improvement of the efficiency of personnel management, the improvement of communications and the creation of more transparent and fair working conditions. However, it also draws attention to potential ethical risks, such as reducing the level of confidentiality of employee data and the possibility of discrimination based on algorithmic decisions. O. Danylenko [2] examines the needs and expectations of young specialists belonging to the so-called Generation Z. The author notes that this group of workers has a high level of technological literacy and expects opportunities for continuous professional development from employers. However, along with these new ethical challenges arise, related to the balance between work and personal life, as well as the issue of equal access to resources for development. Korol S., Polovyk

E. [3] analyze the influence of digital technologies on the professional development of employees. It is pointed out that digitalization contributes to the growth of productivity and increasing the competitiveness of employees. However, the authors also emphasize the importance of ethical aspects, such as the need to ensure equal opportunities for all workers and avoid technological discrimination. Tul S. [4] investigates the emergence of new forms of employment, in particular freelance, remote work and the gig economy. The author emphasizes that such forms of work provide flexibility and new opportunities for employees, but at the same time create new ethical challenges; among them employment instability, lack of social protection and growing inequality. Digitization is an important factor influencing the labor market and is accompanied by numerous ethical issues that require careful consideration. Let's consider the works of foreign scientists, which are devoted to ethical problems related to the digitization of the labor market. Royakkers L. and others. [5] consider the main social and ethical issues arising in connection with digitalization. The authors emphasize the importance of an ethical approach to the integration of digital technologies into the labor market. It is emphasized that automation and artificial intelligence can lead to job losses, income inequality and changes in working conditions. In addition, it is important to ensure that technological innovation does not undermine social justice and workers' rights. Escuredo D. [6] focuses on the future of work in the context of ethics. It is emphasized that the digital transformation of the labor market requires new ethical standards and regulations. One of the key issues is ensuring fair access to new technologies and training employees to adapt to changes. The author also draws attention to the importance of balancing productivity and employee well-being in the digital age. Meireis T. [7] examines the challenges facing work ethics in the context of Economy 4.0 and digitalization. It is noted that digital technologies are changing traditional patterns of employment, creating new forms of work that are often characterized by impermanence and instability. This threatens traditional labor rights and requires a rethinking of ethical standards, in particular, regarding the protection of workers and ensuring their social protection. Pastor-Escuredo D. and others. [8] consider the ethical aspects of the future of work, emphasizing the need to develop such policies and practices that would ensure environmental sustainability and ethics in the digital environment. The authors offer a comprehensive approach to consideration of ethical issues, including not only economic and social, but also environmental aspects. This includes supporting employees in the process of adapting to new technologies and reducing the negative impact on the environment. Sichler R. [9] considers the concept of "New Work" in the context of digital humanism. The author emphasizes that digitalization changes not only the technological aspect of work, but also the ethical and social dimensions. The main emphasis is on how new forms of work organization can contribute to human dignity, autonomy and self-realization. Analyzes how digital innovation can be used to create an ethical

and sustainable work environment that supports diversity and inclusion. Kirchsclaeger P. [10] examines the ethical aspects of the digital transformation of society and the economy from the perspective of human rights. The author emphasizes the importance of ensuring human rights in the process of digital change, including the right to privacy, access to information and protection from discrimination. It is emphasized that digitalization can both improve and worsen the situation of workers, depending on how technological innovations will be implemented. Burr C., Taddeo M., Floridi L. [11] focuses on the concept of digital well-being. The authors analyze how digitalization affects the well-being of employees, in particular, their mental and physical health. Ethical principles for the development and implementation of digital technologies that take into account the well-being of users are proposed. This includes work-life balance, protection against information overload, and providing a conducive working environment. Danaher J. [12] examines the issue of automation and its impact on the future of work. Analyzes how automation is changing the labor market, including the impact on employment, worker skills and economic inequality. The author emphasizes the need to develop ethical strategies to minimize the negative consequences of automation, in particular through the retraining of workers and the creation of new jobs in the digital economy. The importance of ensuring fair working conditions and social security is emphasized. Floridi L. [13] discusses the concept of "Soft Ethics", which emphasizes the need for a flexible approach to the ethical regulation of digital technologies. The author emphasizes that traditional ethical norms may be insufficient in the conditions of rapid development of technologies, which requires adaptive and dynamic ethical standards. This approach is particularly relevant for the labor market, where digital innovations are rapidly changing the structure and nature of employment. Walczak-Duraj D. [14] analyzes the transformation of work under the influence of new technologies. The study focuses on the problems of ethical transgression and unpaid labor in the digital economy. It is emphasized that digitalization contributes to the emergence of new forms of exploitation of workers, which are not always reflected in traditional ethical norms. In particular, it is about the use of unpaid labor in the context of crowdsourcing and the platform economy, which calls for a rethinking of ethical principles in the context of digitalization.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the transformation of ethical norms and principles in the labor market under the influence of the introduction of digital technologies. In this context, it is important to analyze the impact of digitalization on various aspects of the ethical behavior of employees and employers, as well as to identify the key ethical challenges facing the labor market in conditions of digitalization and to develop recommendations for the implementation of ethical norms in the digital environment.

Presenting main material. The acceleration of digital transformation caused by new technologies in the field of digitization is changing the nature of doing

business. While these advances offer significant opportunities for innovation and efficiency in the labor market, they also pose serious ethical challenges. In this vein, we emphasize the critical need for digital ethics in the context of rapid digitization, considering how organizations can balance economic benefits with ethical imperatives to build trust and ensure long-term success.

The wave of digital transformation covers various industries, significantly changing the nature of doing business. The COVID-19 pandemic has further accelerated this trend, requiring the digitization of many work processes. As part of the digitization of the work environment, namely the implementation of artificial intelligence, mass automation, etc., organizations face complex ethical dilemmas that must be resolved in order to maintain public trust and ensure success in the future.

Ethics in digitalization involves the responsible use of technology to balance economic benefits with minimizing harm to customers, employees, and society. Key ethical issues arise related to data privacy, the impact of automation on employment, and accountability

for AI-driven decisions. These questions highlight the importance of integrating ethical considerations into the strategy of digital transformation of the labor market.

Trust is essential to the adoption and success of new technologies and business models. Companies that establish clear ethical standards for digitization can build trust among customers and stakeholders. According to a PwC study [15], responsible digital practices are key to long-term business success. Let's analyze the current state of digital ethics in organizations. The results of the PwC study [15] show that many organizations are not ready for the ethical challenges associated with digitalization (Fig. 1). Only 50% of surveyed companies consider themselves well prepared for ethical challenges under the influence of digitalization, and only 33% positively evaluate their digital transformation. However, a significant majority (82%) are confident in their data protection and security measures, which may be due to the implementation of the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Fig. 1. Business readiness for ethical challenges under the influence of digitalization
Source: compiled on the basis of data from a PwC study [15]

In this context, the role of self-regulation comes to the fore. Organizations cannot rely solely on regulatory frameworks to address digital ethics issues. Proactive self-regulation and adoption of ethical practices are essential to building trust in the marketplace. Working together across industries can help create transparency and common standards, benefiting both businesses and consumers

An important issue in the studied context is the implementation of ethics strategies in the conditions of digitalization. According to PwC research [15], despite

the awareness of the importance of this issue, many companies face challenges in implementing relevant strategies (Fig. 3). The main obstacles are the lack of qualified personnel (56%), insufficient awareness of the concept of ethics in the conditions of digitalization (51%), outdated software (35%), insufficient data security measures (35%). As part of solving these issues, a comprehensive approach is needed, including the integration of digital ethics into existing management systems and ensuring continuous training of employees.

Fig. 2. Challenges in the implementation of ethics solutions in the conditions of digitalization
Source: compiled on the basis of data from a PwC study [15]

As part of the effective integration of digital ethics into business practices, PwC [15] recommends the following actions. The first is to take responsibility, namely to develop and implement a code of digital ethics without waiting for regulatory requirements. The second is to use existing structures, in particular, to integrate digital ethics into existing governance systems, such as risk management and regulatory compliance. The third is to upskill employees, namely to train employees in digital ethics to increase their sensitivity and problem-solving ability. In addition, it is to embed ethics into business processes, including implementing digital due diligence throughout the supply chain and transparently communicating ethical standards. In conclusion, this is value-based product development, which is to apply ethical design principles to prevent risks in the early stages of product development. Accordingly, as digital transformation continues to shape the business environment, digital ethics must become the foundation of an organization's strategy. Companies that proactively address ethical challenges and integrate responsible practices into their operations will be able to build trust, enhance their reputation and achieve long-term success in the digital economy. We emphasize that ethics in digitalization is not only a matter of compliance, but also a strategic imperative that benefits both business and society.

We will offer a toolkit for managing labor market ethics under the influence of digitalization. Note that the formation and implementation of this toolkit is a complex task that requires a complex approach. Let's highlight the key steps and components that should be included in this toolkit. Unit 1 "Analysis of the current situation", which includes an assessment of the state of the labor market, the determination of the impact of digitalization on various industries and professions, as well as the identification of the main ethical issues such as discrimination, transparency of processes and data

privacy. Block 2 "Ethical principles and norms" developed on the basis of universal human values, such as justice, responsibility and respect for human rights. Rules of conduct are established for employers, employees and intermediaries, including recruitment agencies and job search platforms. Block 3 "Regulatory and political mechanisms", which provide for the development and implementation of legislation regulating the use of digital technologies in the labor market, as well as the creation of policies for the protection of personal data of employees. Block 4 "Educational programs", covering the development of courses and training for employers and employees on the ethical use of technology, as well as programs to improve the digital skills of employees. Block 5 "Technological tools", which includes the development and implementation of ethical algorithms to ensure the ethical use of data in the processes of recruiting and personnel management, as well as the creation of platforms for monitoring ethical violations and maintaining compliance with ethical norms. Block 6 "Monitoring and Auditing", which covers regular audits of companies for compliance with ethical standards, as well as establishing mechanisms to collect feedback from employees on ethical workplace practices. Block 7 "Responsibility and Sanctions" includes defining penalties for ethical violations and encouraging companies that adhere to ethical standards through benefits or public recognition.

An example of the construction of such management tools can be a system containing a web application for registration and analysis of ethical incidents, an educational portal with online courses for employees and employers on ethical issues, recruiting algorithms with ethical filters to exclude discrimination based on age, gender or race, as well as automated systems for conducting regular audits of companies for compliance with ethical standards. The proposed toolkit for managing the ethics of the labor market under the influence of digitalization in Table. 1.

Table 1

Toolkit for management of labor market ethics under the influence of digitalization

Bloc	Comments
Block 1. Analysis of the current situation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Assessing the state of the labor market: Determining how digitalization affects different industries and professions. – Identification of major ethical issues: Gathering data on issues such as discrimination, process transparency, data privacy.
Block 2. Ethical principles and norms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Establishment of ethical principles: Development of principles based on universal human values, such as justice, responsibility, respect for human rights. – Standards of conduct: Specification of standards of conduct for employers, employees and intermediaries (recruiting agencies, job search platforms).
Block 3. Regulatory and political mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Regulatory acts: Development and implementation of legislative acts regulating the use of digital technologies in the labor market. – Privacy Policy: Creation of employee personal data protection policies.
Block 4. Educational programs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Training courses: Development of courses and trainings for employers and employees on the ethical use of technology. – Upskilling: Programs to improve the digital skills of employees.
Block 5. Technological tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Ethical algorithms: Development and implementation of algorithms that ensure the ethical use of data in recruiting and personnel management processes. – Platforms for monitoring: Creation of platforms for tracking ethical violations and maintaining compliance with ethical standards.
Block 6. Monitoring and auditing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Audits: Regular audits of companies for compliance with ethical standards. – Feedback: Establish mechanisms to collect feedback from employees on ethical workplace practices.
Block 7. Liability and sanctions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Sanction mechanisms: Determination of punishments for violation of ethical norms. – Incentives for compliance: Encouraging companies that adhere to ethical standards, for example through benefits or public recognition.

Source: own analysis.

In conclusion, the toolkit of management in the key of ethics of the labor market under the influence of digitalization must be flexible, adapted to different conditions and constantly updated according to new challenges and technologies in order to ensure a fair and ethical environment for all participants of the labor market.

Conclusions. Digital transformation, significantly accelerated by the latest technologies in the field of digitization, significantly changes the nature of doing business. The introduction of artificial intelligence, mass automation and other technological innovations open up new opportunities for innovation and efficiency, but at the same time create serious ethical challenges. In the context of rapid digitization, digital ethics are becoming especially important, allowing organizations to balance economic benefits with ethical imperatives, helping to build trust and ensure long-term success.

The COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the digitalization process, requiring the adaptation of many work processes to new conditions. Against this background, ethical challenges have intensified. According to a PwC study, only 50% of companies consider themselves well prepared for digital ethics, and only 33% positively assess their digital transformation. Meanwhile, 82% of organizations are confident in their data protection and security measures, partly due to the implementation of the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

An important aspect is the formation of tools for managing the ethics of the labor market under the influence of digitalization, which includes several key

steps. First of all, it is necessary to conduct an analysis of the current situation, assessing the state of the labor market and identifying the main ethical problems. Based on this, ethical principles and norms are developed, which establish behavioral standards for all participants of the labor market. This is followed by the development of regulatory and political mechanisms, such as legislation and policies for the protection of personal data. An important step is educational programs that include the development of courses and trainings on the ethical use of technology. Technological tools include implementation of ethical algorithms and monitoring platforms. The next step is monitoring and auditing, which includes regular audits of companies for compliance with ethical standards and establishing mechanisms for collecting feedback from employees. Finally, an important component is accountability and sanctions, which include defining penalties for ethical violations and encouraging companies that adhere to ethical standards. The proposed toolkit for managing the ethics of the labor market under the influence of digitalization should be flexible and adaptable to new conditions and technologies in order to ensure a fair and ethical environment for all participants of the labor market. Successfully integrating digital ethics into business practices will help build trust, enhance reputation and achieve long-term success in the digital economy.

Prospects for further research include exploring the potential of combining human and artificial intelligence in managing the ethics of the labor market in conditions of digitalization.

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